

DEVELOPMENT OF A FAILURE CRITERION FOR CAVITATION INDUCED FAILURE UNDER TRANSVERSE LOADING IN MODEL MULTI-FIBER COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Using model composite systems employing a novel cross shaped specimen, matrix cavitation was observed to occur as a function of fiber spacing. The cruciform shaped specimens utilized multiple fibers positioned transverse to the applied load. Analytical results indicate a 3D analogy to the Mohr-Coulomb criterion predicts the observed cavitation initiation.

Keywords: Transverse Failure, Matrix Cavitation, Cruciform Specimen, Mohr-Coulomb

INTRODUCTION

Failure initiation in the plies oriented transverse to the applied load in laminated composite materials is one leading reason for their limited use in primary structural applications. Previous work has indicated that the failure is manifested by either matrix cavitation or fiber-matrix interface debonding. The failure mechanism is not conclusively known and depends on the local stress field of the constrained matrix that is a function of fiber spacing. In this work, the focus is developing the failure criterion for cavitation-induced failure. The cruciform specimen shape design is utilized in a model composite system to observe transverse failure initiation in unidirectional multi-fiber composites when loaded normal to the direction of the fiber.

Cruciform Specimen Geometry

The cruciform-shaped specimen, as shown in Figure 1, nullifies free edge effects that typically dominate the failure of straight-sided specimens under transverse loading, by concentrating the applied load in the center of the specimen. The maximum stress concentration factor for the cruciform shape occurs in the interior region of the specimen, rendering the free edge singularity ineffective because the wings of the specimen carry very little load. Therefore, failure initiates in the central region of the specimen devoid of the influence of the free edge stresses at the fiber ends. In this study, the model composite system consists of single and multi-fiber cruciform specimens. The fibers are located in the cruciform specimen wings and centered with respect to the specimen thickness (t) while extending the full width of the specimen ($2l$). Figure 1 also

shows a schematic of the cross-section of the fiber wing for a multi-fiber specimen. The fiber arrangement in the multi-fiber cruciform specimens entails four fibers located at the corners of a square and a center, fifth, fiber placed at the intersection of face diagonals of the four corner fibers. Fiber spacing (X_{df}) is defined as the center-to-center distance of the corner fibers and is expressed as a multiple of the fiber diameter.

Figure 1: Schematic and nomenclature for cruciform specimen geometry

Model Composite System

The approach for this investigation employs a model composite system consisting of stainless steel wires and two transparent epoxy systems in a cruciform specimen shape. The epoxy systems are a clear, room temperature cured 828/D-230 system and an amber, high temperature cured 862/W system. The 828/D-230 epoxy cures in seven days and has a linear load response. The 862/W epoxy is cured at 121.1°C for 2 hours and 176.7°C for 2 hours and has a non-linear load response. The measured mechanical properties of each matrix system are shown in Table 1.

The fibers of the model composite system are stainless steel wires having a diameter of 0.36 mm. The stainless steel wires are large enough for ease of handling that allows for precise placement to represent resin rich/fiber rich areas common to commercially produced composites. They also allow specimens to be made with specific fiber spacing in order to validate the proposed failure criteria by providing multiple points on the proposed failure surface. The stainless steel wires are known to bond to the resins being

used in this investigation without the use of any surface treatments or sizing. Consequently, no interphase region around the fiber is considered in the cruciform specimen.

Table 1: Matrix mechanical properties

Matrix	Modulus	ν	σ_{yt}	σ_{yc}	τ_y	α_{eff}
828/D-230	3.44 GPa	0.337	61.69 MPa	90.08 MPa	45.60 MPa	741.8×10^{-6}
862/W	2.496 GPa	0.346	77.88 MPa	123.22 MPa	66.38 MPa	67.4×10^{-6}

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE AND RESULTS

Due to the transparency of the model composite system, the experimental technique uses the reflected light method to detect failure initiation in the cruciform shape specimens while tested in tension [1]. Loading is applied in the Y direction by gripping the loading arms of the cruciform specimen, see Figure 1. The reflected light method utilizes the change in light reflected off the surface of the fiber (in the case of fiber-matrix debond) or off the surface of a micro-crack or cavitation (in the case of matrix failure) for initial damage detection. This method, used in conjunction with high-powered video microscopes, allows in-situ observation of the damage initiation and growth [1]. All specimen tests are videotaped to capture the failure initiation and subsequent damage growth to complete fracture of the specimen. Since changes in the fiber spacing will change the failure initiation location due to changes in the stress distribution around the fiber and also due to interaction with its nearest neighbors, multiple video cameras are used to view different areas of the specimen. Consequently, the location of failure initiation for all spatial distributions is captured. A thorough frame-by-frame review of the video with respect to time relates the failure initiation to loading. For further details concerning the reflected light experimental technique, the reader is referred to Foster et al. in reference [1]

Experimental Results

As previously mentioned and indicated in the literature, composite materials subjected to loads normal to the direction of the fiber exhibit either fiber-matrix debonding or matrix cavitation as their first failure mechanism. These two competing damage mechanisms appear to be dependent on fiber spacing. In this work, both mechanisms are observed in cruciform specimens at specific fiber spacing in both matrix systems. The multi-fiber cruciform spacing groups exhibiting fiber-matrix debonding were the $6.0d_f$, $2.5d_f$, $1.9d_f$, $1.57d_f$ and the single fiber specimens in both epoxy systems, as well as the $2.0d_f$ in the 828/D-230 system. The multi-fiber specimens exhibiting matrix cavitation are the $2.0d_f$ in the 862/W matrix and the $1.84d_f$ and $1.75d_f$ in the 828/D-230 matrix. A minimum of 5 specimens were tested at each fiber spacing. A description and specific characteristics of the matrix cavitation damage mechanism follow. The reader is

referred to Foster et al in reference [1] for a detailed description of fiber-matrix debonding

Matrix Cavitation

The matrix cavitation failure initiation is characterized as non-uniform or irregularly shaped micro-voids developing in the matrix under loading due to the triaxial stress state resulting from the constraining influence of the relatively stiff fibers. The light grey or white spots often occur within the matrix area bounded by at least one fiber diameter beyond the volume contained by the corner fibers. They typically happen randomly prior to fiber-matrix debonding. The shape of the spots is random and can vary from a smooth edge circular spot, to a jagged edge oblong shape to even rectangular in shape. The size of the micro-voids can vary as well, usually being a few hundredths of the fiber diameter. Some of the spots often occur at the fiber-matrix interface as evidenced by their relative brighter intensity to those clearly forming away from the interface. However, the cavitation spots do not propagate if it appears they occur at the interface. In addition, they differ in relative intensity at different locations throughout the cruciform specimen. Furthermore, in most of the specimens exhibiting cavitation, multiple cavitations formed prior to final specimen failure. Figure 2 is a photomicrograph of a steel/1.84d_f multi-fiber cruciform specimen exhibiting matrix cavitation. In the white ellipsoids are cavitations developed under a far-field stress of 8.17 MPa whereas the cavitations contained by the black ellipsoids developed under a far-field stress of 12.65 MPa.

Figure 2: Photomicrograph of steel/1.84d_f cruciform specimen showing matrix cavitation and fiber-matrix debonding under a far-field stress of 12.65 MPa

A fracture surface analysis was performed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) for each fiber spacing group to determine any features leading to the first damage mechanism. It is important to note that features on the fracture surface reflect the

fracture initiation and do not necessarily reveal the failure initiation depicted by the videotaped experiments. Analyzing the fractured surface of the cruciform specimens gives clues to the state of stress present at the time of final failure, whereas the videotaped experiments show the failure initiation mode; thus, it is not a 1:1 correlation. Specifically those specimens exhibiting matrix cavitation revealed unique features not seen on the fracture surface of the specimens exhibiting fiber-matrix debonds. Analyzing the failure initiation surfaces observed experimentally along with the fractured specimen surfaces suggest possible stress states present at failure initiation. The results of the fracture surface of the multi-fiber cruciform specimens exhibiting matrix cavitation are shown in Figure 3 for both matrix systems. The white arrows point to the unique cavitation features. Figure 3(a) is of a steel/1.84d_f 828/D-230 cruciform magnified at 230X and Figure 3(b) is of a steel/2.0d_f cruciform magnified at 350X. These features clearly show the presence of tensile and shear forces creating the divot in the matrix away from the fiber edge. The smooth depressed plane of the divot indicates tensile forces acting normal to the fracture surface in the direction of loading while the chevron features emanating from a corner of the divot show a shear stress component. No other failure mechanism features were identified at the fiber spacing exhibiting cavitation in either matrix; thus, these appear to be a direct result of the matrix cavitation observed in the tests.

Figure 3: SEM image of failure initiation (a) steel/1.84d_f 828 cruciform and (b) steel/2.0d_f 862 cruciform

Experimental Results Summary

The two competing failure initiation mechanisms, namely fiber-matrix debonding and matrix cavitation, were observed from the cruciform tests in both matrix systems. Matrix cavitation appears to occur away from the fiber-matrix interface within the limits bounded by one fiber diameter beyond the outer fibers of the fiber group. Fracture surface analysis on the specimens exhibiting cavitation reveal features unique to these specimens. These cavitation features indicate that a combination of shear and tensile stresses are present which would cause these unique sites within the matrix. All specimens exhibiting cavitation also exhibited fiber-matrix debonding as the load was continually applied. The far-field stress at cavitation initiation for the 1.75d_f and 1.84d_f

fiber spacing groups in the 828/D-230 matrix system are 4.67 MPa and 3.97 MPa respectively. The far-field stress at the $2.0d_f$ fiber spacing group in the 862/W matrix system is 7.65 MPa.

ANALYTICAL RESULTS

A 3-D finite element model (FEM) of the multi-fiber cruciform specimens using the ANSYS code is [2] is used to analyze the stress field at the fiber-matrix interface and in the matrix between and around the fibers. Due to the symmetrical fiber arrangement, only 1/8 of the total cruciform specimen is modeled, as shown in Figure 4(a). The subdivisions of the FEM are shown in Figure 4(b). The size ranges between 113,448 to 168,672 elements, depending upon the fiber spacing. The planes of symmetry, namely at $X = 0$, $Y = 0$ and $Z = 0$, are constrained by symmetry boundary conditions, whereas the outer surface is traction-free. The loading is simulated by applying tension perpendicular to the fiber axis (in the Y direction) by means of a constant displacement. The residual stresses due to the matrix cure are accounted for by the application of an effective coefficient of thermal expansion. Details of determining the effective coefficient of thermal expansion for both matrix systems can be found in reference [3]. Table 1 lists the material properties used in the analysis.

Figure 4: 3-D FEM of the cruciform specimen (a) showing mesh model and (b) subdivision details of the FEM

As a starting point for determining the criterion that best describes the observed matrix cavitation occurring in both resin systems, the applicability of each failure criterion to the experimental results will be given. The fractured surface analysis of the specimens exhibiting matrix cavitation indicates a shear presence both at the cavitation sites and generally across the fracture surface. Consequently, it appears that an interaction between the shear and tensile forces is working to create the matrix cavitation. Cavitation causes the formation of micro-voids, which in turn creates a volume increase or dilatation and thus changes the way the material behaves. It has been shown that a

tensile tri-axial stress causes yielding of an epoxy much sooner when compared to uniaxial tension tests [4, 5]. The converse shows that, under a hydrostatic pressure, the strength increases [6, 7]. Analysis indicated that, in the case where cavitation, was observed in the cruciform specimen as the first failure mechanism, the matrix cavitated under a large principal stress bias that created the cavitation features indicating a shear stress presence. The large principal stress bias, the ratios of the first principal stress to the second and third principal stress, indicate that the internal stress state is dominated by a shearing stress. Thus, the stress state in the cruciform specimen would suggest cavitation initiation at a critical shear strength below the matrix shear strength due to the tensile tri-axial stress presence.

Several failure criteria have been proposed in the investigation of matrix failure, specifically cavitation, and are based on the following [4, 5, 7]: a dilatational energy based criterion, a distortional energy-based criterion leading to modifications of the von Mises failure criterion, Eyring's Theory of non-Newtonian flow based criterion, a modified Tresca failure criterion and a Mohr-Coulomb criterion.

Cavitation forming under the stress state developed in the cruciform specimen, as discussed above, would suggest that either the octahedral shear strength or the shear strength in pure shear is the upper limit. Due to the tri-axial stresses present causing dilatation of the material, the limiting shear strength will be reduced at the onset of cavitation. This precludes the dilatational-energy based criterion as it predicts failure to occur only under a tensile hydrostatic state of stress [4]. Furthermore, the authors of this body of work recognize that the competing fiber-matrix debonding type of failure may also be present [4]. For the modified von Mises failure criterion, although it has a distortional basis and includes a term to account for the hydrostatic dependency of polymers, it does not properly reflect the physics creating the matrix cavitation initiation occurring within the cruciform specimen. In the case where the stress state is dominated by a shear stress due to the large bias on the principal stress ratios, the modified von Mises criterion has no upper limiting shear term. The criterion based upon Eyring's theory of non-Newtonian flow at a given temperature and strain rate [4] also does not adequately explain the failure initiation mechanism observed in the cruciform specimens exhibiting matrix cavitation. In the criterion stated in [4], the pressure is expressed as the positive sum of the principal stresses suppressing the flow of the polymer causing an increase in its yield strength. Application of the correct sign for the compressive and tensile yield stresses is not specifically stated in his paper and leads to conflicting results. Consequently, the modified Tresca criterion, expressed in equation (1), and the Mohr-Coulomb criterion, expressed in equation (2), having limiting shear strength terms in their respective criteria, properly reflect the presence of the tri-axial stress at the onset of matrix cavitation. Through the results of the FEM, these two matrix failure criteria will be discussed in further detail for each fiber spacing group in both material systems.

The Modified-Tresca Criterion, as expressed in equation (1), is the critical shear stress, τ_s , at failure using the shear yield stress, τ_s^0 , as determined by torsion experiments and the octahedral normal stress, σ_{on} , determined by the FEM.

$$\tau_s = \tau_s^0 - \mu\sigma_{on} \quad (1)$$

The Mohr-Coulomb Criterion expressed in equation (2) is an expression for the octahedral shear stress at failure, τ_{oct} , using the octahedral shear stress, τ_0 , of the neat

resin absent from any tri-axial stresses acting on the material and is calculated from the neat resin torsion experiments. The octahedral shear stress, σ_{on} , is the mean normal stress determined by the FEA.

$$\tau_{oct} = \tau_o - \mu\sigma_{on} \quad (2)$$

Results of independent neat resin tensile, compression and shear tests are used to evaluate both criteria to see which one best describes the stress state at failure or at the onset of yielding. Table 2 lists the comparison between the Modified-Tresca Criterion and the Mohr-Coulomb Criterion using the neat resin test data. For both matrix systems, the Mohr-Coulomb Criterion predicted the octahedral shear stress at failure initiation better than the Modified-Tresca Criterion predicted the critical shear stress at failure initiation.

Table 2: Criteria comparison using neat resin data

	Mod-Tresca (MPa)	τ_s (MPa)	Δ	% Δ	Mohr-Coulomb (MPa)	τ_{oct} (MPa)	Δ	% Δ
828/D-230								
Tensile	39.83	30.85	9.25	23.2	33.25	29.08	4.17	12.5
Shear	45.61	45.61	0	0	37.24	37.24	0	0
Compression	54.04	45.04	9.01	16.7	43.07	42.46	0.61	1.4
862/W								
Tensile	56.61	38.94	17.67	31.2	48.1	36.71	11.39	23.7
Shear	66.38	66.38	0	0	54.2	54.2	0	0
Compression	80.26	61.61	13.65	17	63.85	58.09	5.76	9

The last test of the criterion is to evaluate it using the FEM analysis and compare it to all the other fiber spacing groups. The locations of cavitation correspond to the exterior matrix (EM) and upper exterior matrix (UEM) of the FEM as shown in Figure 4(b). An apparent critical value of the Mohr-Coulomb Criterion was obtained by FEM results based upon the location of the observed cavitation occurring in the 828/D-230 1.75d_f and 1.84d_f specimens and the 862/W 2.0d_f specimens. The apparent critical value is determined to be 36.35 MPa for the 828/D-230 specimens, while the critical value for the 862/W specimens is 64.14 MPa.

Figure 5 is a plot of the Mohr-Coulomb criterion distribution in the YZ plane of the EM and UEM regions of the FEM for all fiber spacing groups tested in the 828/D-230 matrix system. Also shown in Figure 5 is a plane at the critical value of 36.35 MPa and the vertical lines depict the initial cavitation locations of each specimen cavitating at the 1.75d_f and 1.84d_f fiber spacing. The Mohr-Coulomb distribution reveals that the 1.75d_f, 1.84d_f, 2.5d_f and the 6.0d_f fiber spacing groups exceed the apparent critical value, but only the former two groups' show cavitation as their first failure, the latter two exhibit fiber matrix debonding. Scrutiny of Figure 5 particularly along the direction of loading, Y, at the center of the specimen, Z = 0, shows that the 1.75d_f and 1.84d_f fiber spacing groups have a larger magnitude than the 2.5d_f and 6.0d_f even though all four specimen groups have greater magnitudes than the apparent critical value. Furthermore, the locations of the maximum magnitude of the Mohr-Coulomb criterion correlate very well with the experimentally observed cavitation locations in the 1.75d_f and 1.84d_f specimens and recall no cavitation was observed in either the 2.5d_f or 6.0d_f specimens.

Figure 5: The 828/D-230 Mohr-Coulomb criterion distribution in the YZ plane for all fiber spacing groups tested

Figure 6 is the Mohr-Coulomb distribution in the YZ plane of the cruciform specimen for all fiber spacing groups tested in the 862/W matrix system. Also shown in Figure 6 is a plane plotted at the critical value of the Mohr-Coulomb criterion of 64.14 MPa and the locations of the individual specimen's first cavitation. It is quite clear that the $2.0d_f$ spacing has the maximum magnitude of the Mohr-Coulomb criterion of all fiber spacing groups tested. Careful analysis of Figure 6 shows that the $2.0d_f$ spacing has the maximum magnitude of the Mohr-Coulomb criterion when plotted in the YZ plane at $Z = 0$. The majority of the individual specimens' initial cavitation locations correlate with the analytical results exceeding the critical value of the Mohr-Coulomb as shown in Figure 6.

CONCLUSIONS

A series of experiments and finite element analysis was done to investigate failure initiation of a model composite system when load is applied transverse to the direction of the fiber. Using a novel experimental technique employing a cross shaped specimen with multiple fibers in two transparent epoxy systems, the failure initiation mechanisms, namely fiber-matrix debonding and matrix cavitation, were observed in-situ while being recorded for further analysis. Finite element models of the samples were developed to determine the internal state of stress at failure initiation. Focusing on the matrix cavitation, a failure initiation criterion, identified through the literature search, is carefully selected that best described the physics of the observed cavitation damage. It was found that matrix cavitation is possible, is observed experimentally, and is verified with SEM analysis of the fracture surface. The SEM analysis indicated that a shear

stress component contributes to the cavitation formation. It is shown that the Mohr-Coulomb Criterion, shown in equation (2), verified by independent resin tests, best describe the matrix failure experimentally observed as occurring in the 1.75d_f and 1.84d_f 828/D-230 matrix system and in the 2.0d_f 862/W matrix system.

Figure 6: The 862/W Mohr-Coulomb criterion distribution in the YZ plane for all fiber spacing groups tested

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